

Quality Assurance Mechanisms in Private Schools in Bangkok, Thailand

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Abstract

This study determined the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in private schools in Bangkok, Thailand. Specifically, it examined the profile of private schools in terms of number of enrollees, teaching and non-teaching staff, faculty-student ratio, curriculum used, awards received, and extracurricular activities conducted. The study further assessed the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms in terms of standards of learners' quality, standards of instruction, standards of educational administration and management, and standards of learning and community development. Moreover, the study investigated the significant relationship between the level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms and the schools' profile variables. The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. A purposive sampling technique was employed involving 201 teachers and department heads from selected private schools in Bangkok, Thailand. Data were gathered through a researcher-made questionnaire and analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, weighted mean, and Chi-square test statistics. Findings revealed that the overall implementation of quality assurance mechanisms among private schools in Bangkok was highly implemented with an overall weighted mean of 4.23. Standards of instruction obtained the highest mean of 4.36, followed by standards of learners' quality (4.23), standards of educational administration and management (4.17), and standards of

learning and community development (4.15). Results further showed that certain school profile variables, particularly the number of enrollees, awards received, and extracurricular activities conducted, had significant relationships with the implementation of quality assurance mechanisms. The study concluded that private schools in Bangkok strongly uphold quality assurance standards in promoting effective instruction, learner development, school management, and community engagement. A sustainability plan was proposed to further enhance the implementation of quality assurance mechanisms among private schools in Thailand.

Keywords: quality assurance, private schools, educational management, Bangkok, Thailand, school standards, quality implementation

Introduction

Quality assurance mechanisms play a significant role in ensuring educational effectiveness and institutional sustainability among private schools. In Thailand, private educational institutions continuously strive to maintain academic standards, improve learner outcomes, and strengthen school management systems. This study examined the implementation of quality assurance mechanisms among private schools in Bangkok, Thailand. Specifically, the research focused on standards of learners' quality, instruction, educational administration and management, and learning and community development.

Methodology

The study employed the descriptive-correlational research design. A purposive sampling technique was utilized involving 201 teachers and department heads from selected private schools in Bangkok, Thailand. Data were collected through a researcher-made questionnaire. Statistical

tools used in analyzing the data included frequency counts, percentages, weighted mean, and Chi-square test statistics.

Results and Discussion

The findings revealed that private schools in Bangkok highly implemented quality assurance mechanisms. Standards of instruction obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.36, indicating strong compliance with instructional quality standards. Learners' quality standards garnered a weighted mean of 4.23, while educational administration and management and learning and community development obtained weighted means of 4.17 and 4.15, respectively. Results also indicated that schools highly promoted learners' morality, honesty, environmental awareness, communication skills, creativity, self-learning, and healthy habits. However, selected indicators such as standardized aptitude testing and physical development programs obtained comparatively lower implementation ratings. The study further established significant relationships between selected school profile variables and the implementation of quality assurance mechanisms. Variables such as number of enrollees, awards received, and extracurricular activities conducted significantly influenced the level of implementation.

Variable	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Standards of Instruction	4.36	Highly Implemented
Learners' Quality	4.23	Highly Implemented
Educational Administration and Management	4.17	Highly Implemented
Learning and Community Development	4.15	Highly Implemented
Overall Mean	4.23	Highly Implemented

Conclusion

Private schools in Bangkok demonstrated a high level of implementation of quality assurance mechanisms across learner quality, instruction, administration, and community development. The findings imply that effective quality assurance practices contribute significantly to institutional improvement and educational sustainability. Continuous monitoring and sustainability planning are recommended to further strengthen quality assurance implementation in private schools in Thailand.

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